

Online Supplement:

A temporal refuge from predation can change the outcome
of prey species competition.

Derivation of Analytic Results

Two-Species Competition Model with Constant Predator Density

We outline a model to represent the dynamics of two competing prey species that are subject to predation. The model is based on the classical Lotka-Volterra framework for competing species. The model represents the densities of prey species X_1 and X_2 at time t as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dX_1}{dt} &= (a_1 - q_1(X_1 + c_2X_2))X_1 - b_1X_1 - \mu_1PX_1, \\ \frac{dX_2}{dt} &= (a_2 - q_2(X_2 + c_1X_1))X_2 - b_2X_2 - \mu_2PX_2,\end{aligned}\tag{S1}$$

$$P = K_P$$

3 with μ_i (where $i=1$ or 2) being the predation rates and P the population density of the predator, which we assume is constant. The two-species competition model can be used to represent a scenario in which prey compete in the absence ($\mu_i = 0$) and presence ($\mu_i > 0$) of predation.
6 By setting $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$ we can account for different levels of predation on different species, thus reflecting prey susceptibility and predator preference/attack rate. We assume for simplicity that predation occurs according to a linear functional response (thus we are assuming a generalist
9 predator whose predation does not saturate). We assume a maximum birth rate (a_i) for each species. The birth rate for species i is modified by intra-specific competition from species i , denoted by q_i , and by inter-specific competition from species j , given by c_j . We assume constant
12 natural death rates, b_i .

Steady States

The steady states are found by setting the derivatives in system (S1) to zero and solving the resultant system of equations. There are four steady states in total, which are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (X_1, X_2) &= (0, 0) \\
 (X_1, X_2) &= (X_1^\dagger, 0) \\
 (X_1, X_2) &= (0, X_2^\dagger) \\
 (X_1, X_2) &= \left(\frac{X_1^\dagger - c_2 X_2^\dagger}{1 - c_1 c_2}, \frac{X_2^\dagger - c_1 X_1^\dagger}{1 - c_1 c_2} \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{S2}$$

where X_i^\dagger is the steady state density for species i . When $\mu_i > 0$, $X_i^\dagger = K_i - \mu_i K_P / q_i$, which is the predation-suppressed density for species i in the absence of species j . When $\mu_i = 0$, $X_i^\dagger = K_i$, where $K_i = (a_i - b_i) / q_i$ is the carrying capacity for species i in the absence of species j .

Stability

To assess the stability of the steady states we require the Jacobian matrix for system (S1) (ignoring the constant predator equation).

$$J_{(X_1, X_2)} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - q_1(2X_1 + c_2 X_2) & -q_1 c_2 X_1 \\ -q_2 c_1 X_2 & a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2(2X_2 + c_1 X_1) \end{pmatrix}$$

The following are the eigenvalues and stability conditions for the steady states given in Eqn. (S2):

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Steady State	Eigenvalues	Stability Cond.
(0,0)	$\lambda_1 = a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P$ $\lambda_2 = a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P$	$a_1 < b_1 + \mu_1 K_P$ $a_2 < b_2 + \mu_2 K_P$
$(X_1^+, 0)$	$\lambda_1 = b_1 + \mu_1 K_P - a_1$ $\lambda_2 = a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2 c_1 X_1^+$	$a_1 > b_1 + \mu_1 K_P$ $K_2 - \frac{K_P \mu_2}{q_2} < c_1 (K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1})$
$(0, X_2^+)$	$\lambda_1 = a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - q_1 c_2 X_2^+$ $\lambda_2 = b_2 + \mu_2 K_P - a_2$	$K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1} < c_2 (K_2 - \frac{K_P \mu_2}{q_2})$ $a_2 > b_2 + \mu_2 K_P$
$(\frac{X_1^+ - c_2 X_2^+}{1 - c_1 c_2}, \frac{X_2^+ - c_1 X_1^+}{1 - c_1 c_2})$	$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{1}{2} [-(q_1 X_1^c + q_2 X_2^c) \pm \sqrt{(q_1 X_1^c + q_2 X_2^c)^2 - 4q_1 q_2 X_1^c X_2^c (1 - c_1 c_2)}]$	$K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1} > c_2 (K_2 - \frac{K_P \mu_2}{q_2})$ $K_2 - \frac{K_P \mu_2}{q_2} > c_1 (K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1})$ $0 < c_1 c_2 < 1$

Note: X_i^c denotes the coexistence steady state for species i . The coexistence steady state is
 30 unconditionally unstable when $c_1 c_2 > 1$ and does not exist when $c_1 c_2 = 1$.

Temporal Refuge

33 To consider a temporal refuge from predation we assume the dynamics are represented by equation (S1) with the following criteria for the predation parameter:

$$\mu_i \begin{cases} = 0 & \text{for } 0 \leq t < T_c, \\ > 0 & \text{for } T_c \leq t < T. \end{cases} \quad (\text{S3})$$

The predator continuously switches predation off and on for species 1 and 2 in a periodic
 36 manner, with period T . The length of the temporal refuge is given by T_c during each period. This represents the scenario whereby the predator feeds on primary prey species during the first part of the period and so does not predate on species 1 and 2 for a length of time T_c for each
 39 period.

With this set-up, standard techniques for stability analysis of steady states do not apply.

42 Instead we need to examine the existence and stability of time varying solutions using Floquet theory.

Existence of a Periodic Solution

45 Before we can assess the stability of the solution using Floquet theory, we first need to check that a periodic solution exists. For this, we need to solve the ODE system given above (Eqn. S1) with the time dependent predation parameter (Eqn. S3).

48

Initially we are interested in the periodic solution of species X_1 in the absence of species X_2 . If we consider the periodic steady state $(X_1^*(t), 0)$ with initial conditions $(X_1(0), 0)$, we can ignore
51 the second equation, which gives us:

$$\frac{dX_1}{dt} = (a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - q_1 X_1) X_1,$$

which is a separable equation. We use partial fractions to give:

$$\int \left(\frac{1}{X_1} + \frac{q_1}{a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - q_1 X_1} \right) dX_1 = \int (a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P) dt.$$

The above integral needs to be split into 2: one integral for $\mu_1 = 0$ and another when $\mu_1 > 0$.

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Thus we have:

$$\int_{X_1(0)}^{X_1(t)} \left(\frac{1}{X_1} + \frac{q_1}{a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - q_1 X_1} \right) dX_1 = (a_1 - b_1) \int_0^t dt,$$

and

$$\int_{X_1(T_c)}^{X_1(t)} \left(\frac{1}{X_1} + \frac{q_1}{a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - q_1 X_1} \right) dX_1 = \int_{T_c}^t (a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P) dt.$$

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These integrals can be solved, and rearranged, to give us our periodic solution:

$$X_1(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{K_1 X_1(0) e^{r_1 t}}{K_1 + X_1(0) (e^{r_1 t} - 1)} & \text{for } 0 \leq t \leq T_c, \\ \frac{H_1 X_1(T_c) e^{(r_1 - \mu_1 K_P)(t - T_c)}}{H_1 + X_1(T_c) (e^{(r_1 - \mu_1 K_P)(t - T_c)} - 1)} & \text{for } T_c \leq t \leq T, \end{cases} \quad (\text{S4})$$

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where $r_1 = a_1 - b_1$, $K_1 = r_1/q_1$ and $H_1 = K_1 - \mu_1 K_P/q_1$. By setting $X_1(0) = X_1(T)$ it defines the value of $X_1(0)$ and ensures that the solution is periodic. Figure S1 shows the density of species
 63 1 over a single time period. We can consider the periodic solution for species X_2 in the absence of species X_1 and then the derivation would result in a similar expression, except the subscript 1 would be replaced by subscript 2.

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Stability Analysis

Now that we have a periodic solution, we need to assess its stability. To do this, we need to
 69 linearise (S1) about the periodic steady state $(X_1^*(t), 0)$. If we substitute $(X_1, X_2) = (X_1^* + \epsilon \tilde{X}_1, 0 + \epsilon \tilde{X}_2)$, $\epsilon \ll 1$, into (S1) we get:

$$\frac{d\tilde{X}_1}{dt} = (a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - 2q_1 X_1^*) \tilde{X}_1 - q_1 c_2 X_1^* \tilde{X}_2, \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$\frac{d\tilde{X}_2}{dt} = (a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2 c_1 X_1^*) \tilde{X}_2.$$

From (S5) we can find solutions and create the following matrix:

Figure S1: Plot of the analytic solution for the periodic population density for prey species X_1 (Eqn. S4). Constants were: $r_1 = 3$, $q_1 = 1$ (thus $K_1 = 3$), $K_P = 1$, $\mu_1 = 1$ (thus $H_1 = 2$), $X_1(0) = 2.033$ and $T_c = 1.5$. As can be seen, the final solution $X_1(T)$ reaches the same value as the initial condition, as expected.

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{X}_1^a(T) & \tilde{X}_1^b(T) \\ \tilde{X}_2^a(T) & \tilde{X}_2^b(T) \end{pmatrix},$$

72 where $\tilde{X}_i^a(T)$ denotes solutions after one period of length T with initial conditions $(\tilde{X}_1(0), \tilde{X}_2(0)) = (1, 0)$ and $\tilde{X}_i^b(T)$ the corresponding solutions when the initial conditions are $(\tilde{X}_1(0), \tilde{X}_2(0)) = (0, 1)$. Floquet theory tells us that the steady state $(X_1^*, 0)$ is stable if the eigenvalues of M are less
75 than 1.

For initial conditions $(\tilde{X}_1^a, \tilde{X}_2^a) = (1, 0)$ we know $\tilde{X}_2^a(T) = 0$. Consequently, this means that the
78 eigenvalues of M are given by $\tilde{X}_1^a(T)$ and $\tilde{X}_2^b(T)$. Hence, the following derives an expression for \tilde{X}_1^a and so assesses the stability of the steady state to perturbations in X_1 .

81 Applying the initial condition gives us:

$$\frac{d\tilde{X}_1^a}{dt} = (a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - 2q_1 X_1^*) \tilde{X}_1^a.$$

This is a separable equation that yields:

$$\int_1^{\tilde{X}_1^a(T)} \frac{d\tilde{X}_1}{\tilde{X}_1} = \int_0^T (a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - 2q_1 X_1^*) dt,$$

whose solution is:

$$\boxed{\tilde{X}_1^a(T) = e^{\int_0^T (a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - 2q_1 X_1^*) dt}}.$$

84 If we now set our initial conditions to $(\tilde{X}_1^b, \tilde{X}_2^b) = (0, 1)$ we can find a solution for \tilde{X}_2^b .

We have:

$$\frac{d\tilde{X}_2^b}{dt} = (a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2 c_1 X_1^*) \tilde{X}_2^b,$$

87 which is also a separable equation that gives:

$$\int_1^{\tilde{X}_2^b(T)} \frac{d\tilde{X}_2}{\tilde{X}_2} = \int_0^T (a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2 c_1 X_1^*) dt,$$

whose solution is:

$$\tilde{X}_2^b(T) = e^{\int_0^T a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt}.$$

We know that the eigenvalues of the matrix M are given by $\tilde{X}_1^a(T)$ and $\tilde{X}_2^b(T)$. Hence, the
 90 steady state $(X_1^*, 0)$ is stable if:

$$\tilde{X}_1^a(T) = e^{\int_0^T a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - 2q_1 X_1^* dt} < 1,$$

and

$$\tilde{X}_2^b(T) = e^{\int_0^T a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt} < 1.$$

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These conditions are met if:

$$\int_0^T a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - 2q_1 X_1^* dt < 0,$$

and

$$\int_0^T a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt < 0.$$

which, given the split between the model where the predator is present and where it isn't present,
 96 gives:

$$\int_0^{T_c} a_1 - b_1 - 2q_1 X_1^* dt + \int_{T_c}^T a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 K_P - 2q_1 X_1^* dt < 0,$$

and

$$\int_0^{T_c} a_2 - b_2 - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt + \int_{T_c}^T a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 K_P - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt < 0.$$

Rearranging these 2 expressions gives us our 2 stability conditions:

$$K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) < 2 \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1^* dt, \quad (S6)$$

$$K_2 - \frac{K_P \mu_2}{q_2} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) < c_1 \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1^* dt \quad (S7)$$

where $\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1^* dt$ is the average value of the periodic solution over 1 time period.

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Again, if we assume that species 2 survives instead of species 1, then the above analysis can be repeated to give the corresponding set of stability conditions with indices $\{1, 2\}$ swapped.

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Note, if $T_c = T$ then the above stability conditions revert to those for the system without predation (Eqn. S1, $\mu_i = 0$), whilst if $T_c = 0$ then the conditions revert to those for the predator-prey system (Eqn. S1, $\mu_i > 0$). Thus, these two scenarios provide the limiting cases for the temporal refuge.

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Analysis of Stability Conditions

The above stability conditions require us to know the average population density of either species 1 or 2 (depending on which species survives) when it is at its steady state.

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Consider the first equation from equations S1, with $X_2 = 0$:

$$\frac{dX_1}{dt} = (a_1 - q_1 X_1) X_1 - b_1 X_1 - \mu_1 P X_1. \quad (S8)$$

If we divide throughout the equation by X_1 and integrate both sides of the equation over the interval $[0, T]$ we get:

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$$\int_0^T \frac{1}{X_1} \frac{dX_1}{dt} dt = \int_0^T (a_1 - q_1 X_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 P) dt \quad (\text{S9})$$

$$[\ln X_1]_0^T = (a_1 - b_1)T - \int_{T_c}^T \mu_1 P dt - q_1 \int_0^T X_1 dt. \quad (\text{S10})$$

Since the solution X_1 is periodic $X_1(0) = X_1(T)$ meaning the left hand side of the equation equals zero. Thus:

$$\int_0^T X_1 dt = \frac{a_1 - b_1}{q_1} T - \int_{T_c}^T \frac{\mu_1 P}{q_1} dt, \quad (\text{S11})$$

$$\implies \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1 dt = K_1 - \frac{1}{T} \int_{T_c}^T \frac{\mu_1 P}{q_1} dt. \quad (\text{S12})$$

117 If we assume that the predator density is fixed and the predation rate is constant when $T_c \leq t \leq T$ we have

$$\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1 dt = K_1 - \frac{\mu_1 K_P}{q_1} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right). \quad (\text{S13})$$

Substituting the above expression into the first stability condition gives:

$$K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) < 2 \left(K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) \right), \quad (\text{S14})$$

$$\implies K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) > 0. \quad (\text{S15})$$

120 Thus, the first stability condition requires the temporal and predation reduced carrying capacity to be positive.

123 For the second stability condition we have:

$$K_2 - \frac{K_P \mu_2}{q_2} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) < c_1 \left(K_1 - \frac{K_P \mu_1}{q_1} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) \right). \quad (\text{S16})$$

If we keep $(T - T_c)/T$ together as a single unit, the above expression can be rearranged to give:

$$\frac{T_c}{T} > 1 - \frac{q_1 q_2 (c_1 K_1 - K_2)}{K_P (c_1 \mu_1 q_2 - \mu_2 q_1)}.$$

126 Alternatively, if we keep (T_c/T) as a single unit, basic algebra gives us the inequality in the opposite direction (i.e. $T_c/T < \dots$). Hence, this means we can assume the equality to give us:

$$\boxed{T_{crit}^1 = T \left(1 - \frac{q_1 q_2 (K_2 - c_1 K_1)}{K_P (\mu_2 q_1 - c_1 \mu_1 q_2)} \right)}, \quad (S17)$$

129 as the critical value of temporal refuge needed to ensure the survival of prey species X_1 . Specifically, if $c_1 > c_2$ then T_{crit}^1 is the minimum value required whilst if $c_1 < c_2$ then T_{crit}^1 is the maximum temporal refuge allowed.

132 The above analysis can be repeated for the survival of prey species 2 which gives analogous stability conditions - except with the indices 1 and 2 switched. This gives the following expression:

$$\boxed{T_{crit}^2 = T \left(1 - \frac{q_1 q_2 (K_1 - c_2 K_2)}{K_P (\mu_1 q_2 - c_2 \mu_2 q_1)} \right)}. \quad (S18)$$

135 If the competition coefficients are such that $c_1 c_2 = 1$ then coexistence is impossible. In this case expressions S17 and S18 are equivalent ($T_{crit}^1 = T_{crit}^2$) and they denote the maximum/minimum temporal refuge needed to exclude species 2 for the benefit of species 1. If $c_1 c_2 < 1$ then
 138 the two expressions are not equivalent and the difference in values gives the range of temporal refuge length that allows coexistence. When $c_1 c_2 > 1$ the values of T_{crit}^1 and T_{crit}^2 are such that the better competitor will always out-compete the lesser competitor with no coexistence possible
 141 due to the steady state being unstable.

Furthermore, equations S17 and S18 can be rearranged to give the predator density needed
 144 for species survival under a fixed length of temporal refuge.

Two-Species Competition Model with an Oscillatory Predator

Density

147 The previous analysis assumed the predator was maintained at a constant density. We now show that the analysis can be extended for a general, time varying, oscillatory predator density with the same period as the temporal refuge. The new model is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dX_1}{dt} &= (a_1 - q_1(X_1 + c_2X_2))X_1 - b_1X_1 - \mu_1PX_1, \\ \frac{dX_2}{dt} &= (a_2 - q_2(X_2 + c_1X_1))X_2 - b_2X_2 - \mu_2PX_2,\end{aligned}\tag{S19}$$

$$P = P(t)$$

150 where X_1 and X_2 are the two prey species and $P(t)$ is the general predator density which we assume has oscillatory dynamics with period T .

153 If $\mu_i = 0$ for $i = 1, 2$ then the system reverts to the well studied competitive prey system which has known stability conditions and steady states. When $\mu_i > 0$ the system has a time-varying predator density, which means standard linear stability analysis techniques do not apply. If we
156 impose the condition that the predator density is periodic, with period T meaning the predator density has the same period length as the temporal refuge dynamics, we can use Floquet theory to analyse the stability of the system.

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The analysis is similar to that outlined above, when the predator density remained constant. The linearisation of the system and imposition of different initial conditions follows the same

162 steps as above, except in this instance we get the following solutions:

$$\tilde{X}_1^a(T) = e^{\int_0^T a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 P(t) - 2q_1 X_1^* dt}.$$

$$\tilde{X}_2^b(T) = e^{\int_0^T a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 P(t) - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt}.$$

The stability conditions are met if the following holds true:

$$\int_0^T a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 P(t) - 2q_1 X_1^* dt < 0,$$

and

$$\int_0^T a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 P(t) - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt < 0.$$

which, given the split between the model where predation is present and where it is absent,

165 gives:

$$\int_0^{T_c} a_1 - b_1 - 2q_1 X_1^* dt + \int_{T_c}^T a_1 - b_1 - \mu_1 P(t) - 2q_1 X_1^* dt < 0,$$

and

$$\int_0^{T_c} a_2 - b_2 - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt + \int_{T_c}^T a_2 - b_2 - \mu_2 P(t) - q_2 c_1 X_1^* dt < 0.$$

Rearranging these 2 expressions gives us our 2 stability conditions:

$$K_1 - \frac{\tilde{K}_P \mu_1}{q_1} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) < 2 \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1^* dt, \quad (\text{S20})$$

$$K_2 - \frac{\tilde{K}_P \mu_2}{q_2} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right) < c_1 \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1^* dt \quad (\text{S21})$$

where $\tilde{K}_P = 1/(T - T_c) \int_{T_c}^T P(t) dt$ is the average predator density over the period $T_c \leq t \leq T$ and

168 $\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1^* dt$ is the average value of the periodic solution over 1 time period.

Again, if we assume that species 2 survives instead of species 1, then the above analysis can

171 be repeated to give the corresponding set of stability conditions with indices $\{1, 2\}$ swapped.

Previously we derived an expression for the average density of prey species 1 with a constant
 174 predator. This derivation can be repeated here, except with a time-varying predator density, to
 give:

$$\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T X_1^* dt = K_1 - \frac{\widetilde{K}_P \mu_1}{q_1} \left(\frac{T - T_c}{T} \right),$$

with \widetilde{K}_P defined as above. This means our stability conditions can be rearranged to give:

$$T_{crit}^1 = T \left(1 - \frac{q_1 q_2 (K_2 - c_1 K_1)}{\widetilde{K}_P (\mu_2 q_1 - c_1 \mu_1 q_2)} \right).$$

177 Hence, if the predator density follows a fixed period, with the period potentially being driven
 by alternate prey dynamics, then the average value over the time-frame when predation occurs
 ($T_c \leq t \leq T$) can be used to replace the fixed predator density in the main paper, with all sub-
 180 sequent results remaining the same. If there is variability in the predator density from period to
 period, whilst maintaining the period length, then the value of T_{crit}^1 would need to be updated
 after every period T .

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If the predator density does not occur periodically, or if it occurs on a different time period
 to the temporal refuge, then Floquet theory cannot be used and Lyapunov stability theory needs
 186 to be utilised instead.

Sensitivity Analysis

189 Figure S2 shows results of a sensitivity analysis into the predation rates μ_R and μ_G as well as the
 functional response values V_0 and V_x . The pine marten density required to exclude one species
 in the absence of another (Figure S2(a),(b)) decreases as the predation rate increases. The pine
 192 marten density required to exclude grey squirrels when both squirrels are present (Figure S2(c))
 increases as the red squirrel predation rate μ_R converges towards the grey squirrel predation rate

μ_G . This occurs due to greater predation on red squirrels reducing the competitive pressure on
195 grey squirrels.

In all three instances increased duration of temporal refuge requires greater pine marten den-
198 sity for exclusion.

Figure S2(d) shows how the pine marten density required for grey squirrel exclusion in the
201 presence of red squirrels changes as the functional response parameters, $V_0 = 110 - \delta$ and $V_x =$
 $110 + \delta$, change as δ changes from zero to 110. When $\delta = 0$ the functional response is a step
function and exactly models our theoretical derivation. When $\delta = 110$ the functional response
204 is a linear gradient with no regions of constant response. The pine marten density required to
exclude grey squirrels begins at 0.375 km^{-2} when $\delta = 0$, drops to 0.37 km^{-2} when $\delta = 20$ before
increasing almost linearly upto a maximum density just over 0.415 km^{-2} when $\delta = 110$. Hence,
207 the change in density needed is robust against the change in functional response.

Figure S2: Sensitivity analysis of the pine marten predation rates and functional response for the model represented by equation (7). Here (a) shows the pine marten density needed to exclude red squirrels when there are no grey squirrels present, (b) shows the pine marten density needed to exclude grey squirrels when red squirrels are absent, (c) shows the pine marten density needed to exclude grey squirrels when both squirrels are present in the model and (d) shows the pine marten density needed to exclude grey squirrels, using the full Kielder Forest vole dynamics, as the functional response parameters V_0 and V_x (see Figure 2 in the main text) are altered by the parameter δ , with $V_0 = 110 - \delta$ and $V_x = 110 + \delta$. When $\delta = 0$ there is an abrupt change from predation on squirrels to no predation on squirrels at a vole density of 110 per hectare. As δ increases the change in the predation level on squirrels decreases more gradually with increasing vole density. Note in Figure 2 $\delta = 30$. All results gained using a habitat of 15% broadleaved trees (the remainder being conifers). When not varied in the figure the parameters are as in Figure 4.